

International Journal of Engineering Sciences & Research Technology

(A Peer Reviewed Online Journal)
Impact Factor: 5.164

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**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING SCIENCES & RESEARCH
TECHNOLOGY****PERCEPTION OF HISTORIC DISTRICTS AND HERITAGE STREETSCAPES
PRESERVATION: A CASE STUDY OF JOS AND KADUNA URBAN CENTRES****Ryal-Net, M.B., Israel, G.C., Sati, Y.C. & Ola-Adisa, E.O.***

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3865873

ABSTRACT

Identity question is key to the essence of man existence, his socio-cultural perception, placement status and future destiny. The urban architecture in historic districts of Nigerian city centres requires particular study and contextualization given the current urbanization trend. The paper is a heritage study of selected cities landscapes and their identified historic districts' architectural features along dominant streets of Ahmadu Bello in Jos and Kaduna urban centres. This study undertook an analysis of professionals and inhabitants' perception of some historic buildings along the chosen inner-city streetscape as well as its relevance and value as heritage feature including the preservation exigencies, which are considered most apt for the different traditional value. The methodology adopted critical literature review, observations and documentation through case studies of selected heritage buildings within the two cities significant streets. The study sort professionals opinion in the building industry, including the general public views using a questionnaire. Selected historic buildings and identified respondents were through the use of purposive sampling. The analysis was both descriptive and statistical; using mean values and correlation analysis of the data. The findings affirmed the perceptual value of key streets cityscape in Kaduna and Jos for adaptive preservation of their urban architecture. Furthermore, such preserved features could serve as a medium for tourism adventures and the mark of city-place identity for intergenerational use.

KEYWORDS: Heritages, Historic Districts, Place Making, Streetscape Preservation and Urban Centers.**1. INTRODUCTION**

Urbanism is the unique way of interaction in towns or cities considered as an urban area within a built environment (1). Urbanism is the central beehive of urban life, its organization, problems as well as the technique including the character of the material requirements for urban cultural organization in the form of planning. Conversely, (2) stated that Architecture is the art and science of the built environment and it is key to urbanism or the urban life, dealing with its form, function, and placement in the urban centre. Architecture and urbanism, therefore, work hand in hand as the gradual advancement of one lead to the advancement of the other. Various, heritage district is a geographical area that is either urban or rural, incorporating built ensembles, their sites as well as works of arts or their assortment. They, therefore, have a distinctive character of historical or aesthetic cultural heritage interest or value. Secondly, they represent one or more periods or styles of architecture that is typical of one or more eras in the history of a state or province. Thirdly they cause an area because of such factors to constitute a visibly, perceptible section of the society (3). Such urban characteristic is the context within which the paper considers the historic district's base on visual perceptual rhythm.

Furthermore, (3) posited that historic district is also a definable area which may be urban or rural possessing significant concentration or linkages or continuity of sites, landscapes, structures or objects united by past event or aesthetically by plan or physical development. Such may also be composed of elements separated geographically but linked by association or history. Placemaking architecture is, therefore, a critical identity feature of any town or settlement in all sphere of human endeavour. Historically, city planning utilizes critical road networks as defining features of its setting in addition to the zoning of the various spaces and functional units (4; 5&6). The historic district is defined using road networks, which also serves as a prism within which to conceptualize the cityscape. Therefore, the zoning units in terms of districts and the road arteries concerning streets are the livewire of a city setup and indeed its heritage features' and visualization (7).

City layout in Nigeria settlements is made up of essential components depending on whether they are in the Northern part of the country, Eastern Region or the Western part. In Northern Nigeria, particularly the old Hausa city-states, virtually all settlements have Central Mosque, Emir Palace and Market Place as the centre of

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the city, then radially surrounded by residential areas. At the periphery, we have the farmlands for important crops all within the city walls. In such city-state, various zones interconnect with arterial roads, which serve as the access and medium of visualizing its setting. Subsequently, as the cities grow, Northern Nigeria old cities were mostly left intact, while the Tudun Wada and Sabon-Gari's areas evolved to accommodate other Northerner's settlers and Southerners, respectively (8). Similarly, in Eastern Nigeria, most old settlements have a village square where all social activities as well as market is located. Homesteads are build surrounding the core which serves as the hearth for the various communal events. While farmlands and other household structures are intertwined leading to the settlement outskirts. (8) further argued that comparable situations were replete in the case of the Western and Mid-Western Regions of old Nigeria, best exemplified by the Benin city and Ile-Ife settlements. Activity zoning was the actual city planning reality in Nigeria before the colonialization and subsequent amalgamation of the Northern and Southern Protectorate into today's Nigeria. (9) and (10) also observed that with the coming of the colonial master, they introduce their urban planning concept with the zoning of Commercial, Industrial, Administrative areas, Residential settlements and recreational zones. Furthermore, the concept of residential segregation based on race, where white colonialist stay in Government Reserved Areas (GRAs) became prominent. It is worthy to state however that some cities were virtually new settlement as a result of the colonial administrative convenience as in the case of Kaduna colonial town and mining outpost as the case of Jos city (11; 12 &13). (11), further affirm that since the post-colonial era, Jos Metropolis had gone through unprecedented growth and development. However, significant colonial buildings on streetscapes have remained the dominant identity features; thereby defining the historic place of the city and the perception by its inhabitants. Since the colonial towns were mainly planned and build to serve the colonialist exigencies and are a reflection of their socio-economic and administrative preferences, a reconceptualization of the current and future identity frame in Nigerian urban centres is required. The colonial cities of Jos and Kaduna are the concern of this study as well as its context given the current trend and the significance of place identity architecture. The place identity architecture should be an expression of the people socio-cultural and economic value preference. Otherwise, the unique historic identity features and viewpoint will gradually be globalized and become non-existent.

Statement of the Problem

The challenging globalization reality and the evolving indigenous and regionalist tendencies are clearly at a point of conflict, particularly in most former colonies. Major historic districts in most developing countries of colonized urban centres are a reflection of the colonialist socio-cultural, economic and political preferences with counterfactuals (14). In establishing an informed and proactive placemaking process for our urban centres, deliberate effort in evolving a unique morphological identity is required(15). Such effort becomes necessary considering that more than half a century after the independence of Nigeria from Britain, the colonial heritage buildings are still the principal visual architectural features dominating the major cities streetscapes; despite the acclaim economic growth and expansion of post-colonial Nigeria (16; 17). Before appropriate placemaking strategies attainment, there is the need to identifying the current heritage realities on the significant streetscape of selected urban centres in the case of Kaduna and Jos metropolis. The identified features within a streetscape will serve as an impetus for the study subject. After that, the research will establish the critical cognitive historic architectural morphological features in terms of their form and function, aesthetics, the material used as well as the fenestration. These features could serve as reinforced identity markers by the urban dwellers in visualizing their architectural place. That is as a result of the growing interest in urban centre identity regarding historic districts documentation (18). Ultimately the concern of examining the perceptual value of historic districts and streetscapes will give a better and well-informed understanding of the phenomena of placemaking. It is particularly so in the aspects of the interaction of the socio-cultural value of professionals and city dwellers of the historical place within the selected heritage buildings. Similarly, the political, economic and environmental significance of these buildings along the significant streetscape will serve as an essential indicator of the dwellers' sense of identity and possible influence on the placemaking strategy by government and other developers in our urban centres.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study aim is to critically review the historic districts and architectural heritage streetscapes towards preservation of Jos and Kaduna urban centers for place identity making. Specifically, the paper would therefore;

- (a) Identify architectural heritage features of historic districts along Ahmadu Bello ways in Jos and Kaduna.
- (b) Establish the visual identity status of architectural features in historic districts along Ahmadu Bello Way in Jos and Kaduna.

- (c) Examine the morphology of historic districts architectural features for the heritage streetscape preservation in Jos and Kaduna.
- (d) Ascertain architectural heritage value perception of historic districts and their streetscape preservation in Jos and Kaduna.

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

The two principles of intelligent urbanism, which is the balanced nature and tradition are the pure intent of this study. Nature balance has to do with emphasising the distinction between utilising resources and exploiting them. It also promotes environmental assessments to identify fragile zones, threatened ecosystem and habitats enhancement through conservation, density control, land use planning and open space design. The traditional balance is concern with interventions on existing cultural assets, respecting traditional practices and precedents of style, wisdom in the layout of human settlements and promotes architectural styles and motifs (19; 20). Architectural theory of place visualised place as a concept and not as a phenomenon, in distinguishing between place as a phenomenon and place as a concept, *the* paper approach place as a target for study and probable theorisation. Place as we experience daily is as "things in the world" (21:25). Here, identified locations within the physical environment by names having unique characteristics and often subjected to evaluation and "wrapped in common sense" (22:1). It is the common sense of perception by critical stakeholders that this study desires to examine. Common sense is considered significant for better understanding of the phenomena of place-making in historic districts of colonial urban Nigerian streetscapes.

Conversely, place as a concept it is viewed as "a way of understanding the world" (23:11). Therefore, place concept is the general abstraction that is the representation of the shared characteristics of specific place phenomena. Just as there are many different place phenomena in the world, there can be multiple understandings of place as a concept. Place phenomena are thoroughly integrated with our everyday live sand may require no awareness of their possible conceptualisations to be of effect or importance. It might not be needful to acquire intelligent appreciation of what makes a place a place so as to understand particular places. "Place as a concept cannot be considered in depth without reflecting upon how it is manifested and experienced as a phenomenon" (24:8). It is these perceptual conceptualisation of placemaking that this study pursued with the built industry professionals and current inhabitants of the selected buildings.

The concept of place is, therefore, both physical as well as psychological. The physical form which mainly deals with aesthetic, functionality, and form, while activity entails social, economic, commercial and environmental and meaning states place identity, perceptual understanding value; these can integrate to form the placemaking concept (25). In this study, the placemaking is concerning historic colonial urban centres streetscape and their strategic preservation process. In the context of environmental psychology, however, the place is predominantly defined by a physical environment constructed based on its interrelationship with individual's internal psychological and social processes and attributes and activities done at the place(26). The place could not be separated from people who make places and invest meanings in them as stated in (3), which contended that "places are also interpreted, narrated, perceived, felt, understood, and imagined." It is apparent that without addressing the significance of the people's psychological connection with places, any form of assessment in determining place quality will be inadequate thus the conceptualised placemaking framework for the study as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Typologies of Historic Districts Heritage Streetscape Preservation for Place Making

Source: Adapted from (Dovey, 2010; Montgomery, 1998; Norsidiah & Khalilah, 2015).

Consequently, preservation activity should achieve three objectives: firstly, maintaining continuity of essential aspects of the culture; secondly, facilitating a desirable level of growth and change in both physical and socio-economic environments; and thirdly, through achieving the first two. These make preservation less strenuous as a development endeavour. It is significant to know what is continuing, modified and how the modification matches the continued aspects of the culture for cultural continuity and change. The dynamics of cultural change should be less strenuous and manageable for the predictability. What is, however, significant for this study is the actual perceptual value by the critical stakeholders of our historic urban streetscape for preservation and identity niche. Towards maximising the gains from the moderated rate of place dynamics, its flexibility in management, maintenance of resources and their utilisation as well as time, organisational support and policy frame is critical. Furthermore, it should consider all groups of society as stakeholders and their expectations. Strategic historic district streetscape preservation can adopt the conceptual framework for its perceptual assessment of the study area streetscape as the basis for establishing the study position. Placemaking may not require drastic change, but to be more realistic about the preservation program in terms of need, objectives, limits, means, and outcome need stating for all stakeholders (27; 28&29).

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research design is the use of cross-sectional correlational case study and survey, where the research variables are not manipulated but collected from two different study groups (30; 31). The study was undertaken in Jos and Kaduna urban centres within the period of 15th November 2018 to 20th January 2019. The study areas most probably harbour some of the best expression of the colonialist influence on built heritage in this part of the country. The two cities were at inception scantily settled by various indigenous communities before the Europeans adventure for economic and political as well as administrative convenience (32; 33 &34). Jos is renown as the Tin mining city located in North Central Geo-Political Zone of Nigeria and is the Plateau State Capital. Jos has a characteristically hilly landform having several rock outcrops accompanied by low laying areas dotted with abandoned mining ponds. Kaduna, on the other hand, grew first as an administrative centre of the North, then as its military stronghold and still stands today as the rallying centre of Northern administrative, military and political activities.

The studied sample architectural features were selected based on expedient stratified purposive random sampling (35). Parameters used are period of construction, type of materials used, the function of the structure initially and currently, magnitude of the structure (size, area and height) as well as the status of buildings preservation. Similarly, built environment professional was purposively selected contingent on the preliminary discussion as to the level of familiarity with the chosen buildings. The professionals' survey respondents considered included; architects, engineers, surveyors and other persons based on their acquaintance with

Ahmadu Bello Way in Jos or Kaduna. Also selected buildings occupant respondents' availability and willingness to participate at the time of visiting the selected buildings were paramount determinant.

For this study, the Jos Ahmadu Bello Way shall mainly be from the ECWA Good News Junction to the point the Road terminates at the Post Office Junction and continues as Beach Road. The other part of the Road terminates around Bukuru Park from ECWA Good News Church junction, most of the buildings here are residential quarters, therefore, were not considered as part of the study area. The principal streetscape architectural features of concern are institutional, commercial and administrative buildings along the Ahmadu Bello Way. The structure purposively selected for Jos include; Redeemed Christian Church of God (Former REX Cinema), Ministry of Works Workshop, Post Office Building, Open stall (SCOA Plaza). It is worthy to state that residential buildings also adorn this segment of the Ahmadu Bello way that is currently mostly used for commercial purposes but do not form part of the selected sample.

The architectural features purposively selected along the length of Ahmadu Bello Way Kaduna were from Bank PHB Roundabout through NEPA and Leventis Roundabout then ending at Broadcasting Road by KASUPDA building. This segment of Ahmadu Bello Way in Kaduna forms the chief streetscape for commercial activities within the city centre. It is worthy to state that buildings along this segment of the Road are the dominant ones within the cityscape for the period of the street existence. The architectural heritage buildings selected are; UTC building, Unity Bank Building, Nigerian Airways, Lennard's (Bhojsons), Bata, Niger House, Leventis Building and KASUPDA Building. The instrument of Data Collection were field Survey and case study observations which described the buildings condition as well as the streetscape perceptual identity of the Ahmadu Bello Way in Jos and Kaduna. Seventy questionnaires were prepared based on Sekaran (2011) advice where a large sample might not be feasible a sample size of at least 30, and at most 500 is acceptable. The questionnaires elicited responses and relevant information to the study variables in terms of a five-point perceptual summated rating scale (31). Fifty-one (51) questionnaire was filled and returned for analysis, which is 73% and thus considered adequate (36; 37).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study research data is the result of questionnaire responses base on professionals and other respondents' perception of the studied streetscapes. Identified architectural features are those of the historic districts heritage street for preservation within the cities of Jos and Kaduna. It is, however, worthy to note that these were the most preferred and prominent architectural features chosen purposively from a list of the identified historic district architectural features that marked the streetscape and served as their heritage which require preservation to reaffirm the place making identify of each street and the urban centres.

The questionnaire survey had mean values assigned to the response options as highly significant (5), Significant (4), Uncertain (3), Insignificant (2) and Highly Insignificant (1) as shown in the tables. Therefore, a mean value higher than three connotes that majority of the respondents' perception indicated acceptance to the mentioned opinion otherwise disagreed when the mean value is less than 3.

Table 3, indicated that the majority of Kaduna resident believed that the visual identification of architectural features in historic districts along Ahmadu Bello Way is significant. The visual identification of historic districts that gave meaning to its places goes through identification, perception and understanding, which gives meaning. The process considered that the average response rate is higher than the threshold of 3. The table also depicts respondents' opinion on how they visually identify the selected historic district architectural features along Ahmadu Bello Way in Jos, which similarly indicated that majority of the respondents considered the architectural features visually significance in the historic districts along Ahmadu Bello Way. The response was on the average response rate that is greater than the threshold of 3.

Table 3: Respondents significance visual identification of the architectural features in historic districts along Ahmadu Bello streetscape in Kaduna and Jos?

Architectural features	Mean Response	Std. Dev	Remark
Kaduna	4.20	0.34	Significant
UTC (Stanbic IBTC) building	4.35	.93	Significant
Bank of the North (Unity Bank)	4.26	1.01	Significant
New Nigeria Newspaper Building	4.43	.99	Significant
NDIC Buildings	3.52	1.50	Significant
Nigerian Airways Building	3.70	1.36	Significant
Lennards (Big Treat)	4.13	1.14	Significant
Bata Building (Thermocool Showroom)	4.22	1.00	Significant
Niger House (Former Skye Bank)	4.22	.95	Significant
Leventis Building	4.61	.78	Significant
Chellarams (Electronics shop)	3.91	1.04	Significant
Leventis Buildings (Electronics Shops)	4.52	.90	Significant
KASUPDA office	4.52	.95	Significant
Jos	4.25	.16	Significant
Post Office	4.86	.36	Significant
Ministry of Works Workshop	4.29	.64	Significant
SCOA Warehouse (Open stalls)	4.10	.83	Significant
Residential Building (The Net Café)	4.86	.36	Significant
Bata (Shops)	4.00	.84	Significant
Chartered Bank (IBTC Bank)	3.67	1.28	Significant
Lennards Shoes (DunJos Pharmacy)	4.05	.22	Significant
REX Cinema (RCCG)	4.10	.83	Significant

Table 4 depicts respondents' opinion on observation of the morphology of historic district's architectural features for heritage street preservation in Jos with respect to their Visual Aesthetics, Form and Function, Materials/Finishes, Fenestration/openings for each aforesaid building sited in Ahmadu Bello way, Jos, thus since the average response rate are all greater than the threshold 3, this can be deduced that majority of the respondents considered morphology of historic district's architectural features as significant for heritage street preservation of selected buildings in Jos.

Table 4: Respondents opinion on the morphology of historic district's architectural features for heritage street preservation in Jos

Building/Morphology attributes	Mean Response	Std. Dev	Remark
Post Offices	4.55	.24	Significant
Visual Aesthetics	4.38	.50	Significant
Form and Function	4.33	.48	Significant
Materials/Finishes	4.86	.36	Significant
Fenestration/openings	4.62	.50	Significant
SCOA Warehouse	4.06	.51	Significant
Visual Aesthetics	3.43	.93	Significant
Form and Function	4.14	.36	Significant
Materials/Finishes	4.67	.48	Significant
Fenestration/openings	4.00	.32	Significant
Rex Cinema	4.41	.19	Significant
Visual Aesthetics	4.38	.92	Significant
Form and Function	4.19	.75	Significant
Materials/Finishes	4.62	.67	Significant
Fenestration/openings	4.43	.60	Significant

Table 5 depicts respondents' opinion on observation of the morphology of historic district's architectural features for heritage street preservation in Kaduna with respect to their Visual Aesthetics, Form and Function,

Materials/Finishes, Fenestration/openings for each aforesaid building sited in Ahmadu Bello Way, Kaduna, consequently since the average response rate are all greater than the threshold of 3, this suggested that majority of the respondents opinion on morphology of historic district's architectural features is significant for heritage street preservation of buildings in Kaduna state.

Table 5: Respondents opinion on the morphology of historic district's architectural features for heritage street preservation in Kaduna

Building/ Morphology Attributes	Mean	Std. Dev	Remark
Bank of the North (Unity Bank)	3.54	1.32	Significant
Visual Aesthetics	3.79	.86	Significant
Form and Function	3.72	.70	Significant
Materials/Finishes	3.55	.74	Significant
Fenestration/openings	3.10	.72	Significant
NDIC Building	3.84	0.12	Significant
Visual Aesthetics	3.87	.63	Significant
Form and Function	3.93	.64	Significant
Materials/Finishes	3.90	.71	Significant
Fenestration/openings	3.67	.71	Significant
Leventis Building	3.38	0.15	Significant
Visual Aesthetics	3.47	1.11	Significant
Form and Function	3.47	.78	Significant
Materials/Finishes	3.43	.82	Significant
Fenestration/openings	3.17	1.18	Significant
Chellarams Building	3.33	.08	Significant
Visual Aesthetics	3.27	.83	Significant
Form and Function	3.37	.72	Significant
Materials/Finishes	3.43	.73	Significant
Fenestration/openings	3.27	.74	Significant

The result in Table 6 depicts respondents' value perception significance of historic districts and their heritage streetscapes preservation of building along Ahmadu Bello Way in Jos and Kaduna state, with respect to their Architectural, Socio-Cultural, Historical, Economic and Environment value. Thus since above mean response rate is greater than the threshold value 3 in both locations, it therefore showed that the finding confirms majority of the respondents sampled in Kaduna and Jos revealed that there is significant Architectural, Socio-Cultural, Historical, Economic and Environment value of historic district heritage streetscape features and preservation along Ahmadu Bello way in Jos and Kaduna respectively.

Table 6: Respondents Urban Heritage Value Perception of Historic Districts and their Streetscapes Preservation in Jos and Kaduna.

Value Perception	Mean response	Std. Dev	Remark
Kaduna	4.17	.17	Significant
Architectural	4.23	.82	Significant
Socio-Cultural	4.13	.63	Significant
Historical	4.13	.82	Significant
Economic	4.23	.68	Significant
Environment	4.13	.73	Significant
Jos	4.16	.50	Significant
Architectural	4.86	.36	Significant
Socio-Cultural	4.33	.48	Significant
Historical	3.48	1.66	Significant
Economic	4.05	.22	Significant
Environmental	4.10	.89	Significant

Findings and Discussions

The study has been able to establish that;

- (a) The acquired visual identification of architectural features in Kaduna and Jos historic districts along Ahmadu Bello Way were considered significant. Therefore, it is considered as most relevant for historic streetscape preservation that ensures place identity acquired meaning through place identity, perception and the understanding of its value within the urban centres.
- (b) The morphology of historic districts of Jos and Kaduna in respect to visual aesthetics, form, function, material/finishes and fenestration is considered significant in preserving their heritage streetscape and place identity.
- (c) The Urban Heritage value perception of historic districts for streetscape preservation is considered significant. Therefore, the features within these historic districts require preservation for them to continue to define the general place meaning and essence of the city streetscapes.

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Almost sixty years after independence, the vital urban identity features in most Nigerian cities are mostly colonial heritage and its neo-colonial features. These features mark significant commercial streetscapes and are also visibly reflected within the historic districts in terms of the Government Reserve Areas (GRAs). Considering the visual perception of the urban form has enormous socio-cultural, economic and political implication for the present and future generations; there is the urgent need for deliberate architectural masterpieces being designed, constructed or readapted for use as a reflection of the actual national heritage and identity. Such deliberate urban regeneration could change and redefine while preserving the historic features towards the appropriate assignment of the placemaking process of Urban Architecture in Jos and Kaduna metropolis. Based on the study findings this paper, therefore, recommends as follows;

- (a) That urban regeneration should be in such a way as to preserve the vital historical districts identity features while imposing the national character of the city along its streetscape. Here government agencies and professionals in the industry and the developers can be of high relevance in ensuring the attainment of this noble goal of a national place identity within its urban centres.
- (b) Remodelling and renovation should always aim at imposing a visual ideal that is unique to the city considering the significance of the visual value of the streetscape
- (c) . Unique visual ideal will guarantee an architectural heritage value and a distinctive morphological outlay. These can be achieved through deliberate urban planning policy and implementation strategy by relevant agencies and professionals.
- (d) Urban architectural heritage value perception of historic districts for streetscape preservation for Kaduna and Jos should consider architectural, socio-cultural, historical, economic and environmental factors towards preservation of the historic district of Jos and Kaduna urban centres. Urban designers and architects must always consider these critical factors in the processes of preserving the place identity of the two urban centres.
- (e) Any preservation activity should be defined using the set guideline, hence the need for Jos Metropolitan Development Board (JMBD) and Kaduna State Urban Property Development Agency (KASUPDA) to review guidelines for developments along historic district and ensure strict adherence. Such decisive action could preserve the streetscape identity features and also plant an enduring place identity for each of these cities.

Further studies could be concerning the interrelationship between the critical study variables in placemaking, concerning morphology, place value and visual identification attributes. It is such a study that could expand and unravel additional linkages and their implications for place-making of specific historic districts in urban centres of Nigeria.

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